

LEADERSHIP COMPETENCE OF SUPREME PUPIL GOVERNMENT OFFICERS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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Leadership Competence of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Development Program

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Abstract

This study entitled Leadership Competence of Supreme Pupil Government Officers in Relation to Academic Performance: Basis for Development Program, determined the level of competence of SPG officers in planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation in relation to academic performance. Respondents were 103 SPG officers in eight elementary schools. Descriptive-correlative research design was used. Data were collected using the standardized questionnaire of Arribado (2019). Results revealed that SPG officers comprise mostly of 12-13 years old, female, grade six pupils, with complete set of officers. Respondents were mostly poor. Level of leadership competence was high. Level of leadership competence in terms of profile was high. Academic performance was outstanding. No significant difference in the level of leadership competence of SPG officers according to age sex, and grade level, but significant difference existed in position and socio-economic status, and there was no significant relationship between the level of leadership competence and academic performance of SPG officers.

Keywords: *leadership, academic performance, development program*

Introduction

Student government is an essential aspect of education that provides students with a platform to express their opinions and ideas and participate in their school community's decision-making process. Student government plays an important role in promoting student involvement and empowerment in their education and is a valuable part of the school experience for many students. It allows them to develop leadership skills, work with their peers, negotiate and communicate effectively to achieve their goals (Jafrin, 2023).

Patrick (2022) detailed that education researchers need to contribute to meaningful student leadership that avoids exploiting or tokenizing student voices and to recognize student leadership activities as real politics and ensuring that education institutions and societies provide education decision-making structures sufficient for effective student leadership to take place (Patrick, 2022).

The Department of Education (DepEd), through DepEd Order No. 47, series of 2014, recognizes the significant role and contributions of the Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) in the schools, believing in the need for a better and organized pupil organization and in the development of the youth as future leaders of the nation.

Serving as a formal structure and highest governing student body in schools, SPG is founded on the principles of participatory government, responsible servant-leadership, collaboration, unity, accountability, and efficiency in serving the student body, and is committed to putting these values, principles, and ideals into action through academic, socio-civic, leadership programs, and activities (Arribado, 2019). The schools are likewise charged to enhance and encourage students to become future leaders beyond the formal pillars of the school institution (DepEd Order, 11, s. 2016).

It was observed in school, however, that the SPG candidates and officers were not completely aware of their powers, duties, and responsibilities inasmuch as they were not provided with leadership seminars and training, thus, leaving them oblivious of their leadership roles. It is on this premise that the researcher was motivated to study the leadership competence of the elected SPG officers and to find out how they perform their duties and responsibilities in terms of planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study was to determine the leadership competence of Supreme Pupil Government (SPG) officers in District IV, Division of Bacolod City for school year 2023-2024 and its relation to their academic performance. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of SPG officers in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. grade level;
 - 1.4. position; and
 - 1.5. economic status?
2. What is the level of leadership competence of SPG officers in terms of:
 - 2.1. planning;

- 2.2. implementation;
- 2.3. monitoring and evaluation; and
- 2.4. student representation?
3. What is the level of leadership competence of SPG officers when grouped according to their profiles?
4. What is the overall academic performance of SPG officers?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of leadership competence of SPG officers when grouped according to their profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of leadership competence of SPG officers and their academic performance?
7. Based on the results of the study, what development program may be prepared?

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilized the descriptive-correlative research design. It aimed to investigate the link between variables and their association, hence, was suitable. According to Stangor (2011), descriptive research provides a snapshot of the current thoughts, emotions, or behaviors of individuals, and its benefits include providing a relatively complete picture of what is occurring at a given time and allowing the development of questions for further research.

Respondents

The subjects and respondents of this study were the one hundred three Supreme Pupil Government Officers of eight elementary schools in District IV in the Division of Bacolod City for school year 2022-2023.

The population of the study was composed of the one hundred three total number of Supreme Pupil Government officers elected for school year 2022-2023. With this number, the researcher has decided to use the purposive sampling method and therefore considered all the officers as respondents of the study.

Table 1 presents the schools and the corresponding number of SPG officers.

Table 1. Distribution of SPG Officers per School in District

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Number of SPG Officers</i>
1 Antonio L. Jayme Elementary School	13
2 Felisa Elementary School	11
3 Graciano Lopez Jaena Elem. School	16
4 Handumanan Elementary School I	15
5 Handumanan Elementary School II	12
6 Jose J. Gonzaga Elementary School	12
7 Kabugwason Elementary School	12
8 Paglaum Village Elementary School	12
Total	103

Instrument

The data-gathering instrument of this study was a standardized questionnaire used in the study of Arribado (2019) on the Efficacy of Supreme Student Government in Secondary Schools. The questions were based on the powers, duties, and responsibilities of SSG as stipulated in the Constitution and By-Laws of the Supreme Student Government or SSG (Department of Education, 2016). However, at the recommendation of the panel members during the pre-oral defense, questions were translated to Hiligaynon to suit to the level of understanding of the officers of the SPG who were all in the elementary level.

The first part of the research instrument aimed to gather information of the demographic profile of the SPG officers on age, sex, grade level, position in SPG, and socio-economic status.

The second part proposed to measure the leadership competence of SPG officers in the categories of planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation with items in every category answered by the respondents. On the other hand, the pupils' grades during the second quarter of school year 2023-2024 were used to measure classroom performance.

Procedure

To gather the data needed in this study, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent (see Appendix B). With the granted request, the researcher met with the advisers and the pupil-respondents and provided them with an orientation. The researcher then asked the SPG officers to respond to the survey and were assured of the complete confidentiality of their answers. At the completion of the survey, questionnaires were promptly retrieved, and the data were collected and recorded in preparation for presentation, analysis, and interpretation.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the examination of the gathered and organized information in terms of characteristics, patterns, trends, differences,

similarities, and relationships that answer the research question or meet study objectives. Data gathered were organized, analyzed and interpreted to provide necessary information to describe and test the hypothesis, which utilizes statistics to add clarity and meaning to the analysis of data (Ariola et al., 2006). To obtain the needed data for the study, the following specific problems needed analysis using the following corresponding statistical tools.

For statement of the problem 1, on the profile of the SPG officers in terms of age, sex, grade level, position, and socio-economic status, frequency count and percentage were appropriate to use.

For statement of the problem 2, on the level of leadership competence of SPG officers in terms of planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation, the mean was also used.

For statement of the problem 3, on the level of leadership competence of SPG officers in terms of planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation, the mean was also used.

For statement of the problem 4, on the SPG officers' academic performance when grouped according to their profile, the computed average grades of the pupils were utilized.

For statement of the problem 5, on the significant difference in leadership competence of SPG officers when grouped according to planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation, the use of Kruskal-Wallis H-Test applies.

For statement of the problem 6, on the significant relationship between the leadership competence of SPG officers and their academic performance, Goodman-Kruskal's Gamma (G) was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered. The data were arranged comprehensively to answer the statement of the problem using different statistical tools.

Profile of Supreme Pupil Government Officers

The table that follows shows the demographic profile of Supreme Pupil Government officers in terms of age, sex, grade level, position, and socio-economic status.

Table 2. *Demographic Profile of Supreme Pupil Government Officers*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	8-9 years old	1	1.0
	10-11 years old	30	29.1
	12-13 years old	54	52.4
	14-15 years old	18	17.5
	Total	103	100.0
Sex	Male	24	23.3
	Female	79	76.7
	Total	103	100.0
Grade Level	Grade III	4	3.9
	Grade IV	15	14.6
	Grade V	38	36.9
	Grade VI	46	44.7
	Total	103	100.0
Position	President	8	7.8
	Vice President	8	7.8
	Secretary	8	7.8
	Treasurer	8	7.8
	Auditor	8	7.8
	Health Protocol	16	15.5
	Grade Level Representative	39	37.9
Socio-Economic Status	Total	103	100.0
	Poor	61	59.2
	Middle	37	35.9
	Rich	5	4.9
	Total	103	100.0

Table 2 reveals that in terms of age, out of 103 officers of the Supreme Pupil Government, 54 or 52.4% belong to 12-13 years old group, 30 or 29.1% are 10-11 years old, 18 or 17.5 percent are 14-15 years old.

The data imply that, regardless of their age, all pupils can be leaders, although their roles and responsibilities appropriately vary. This is an indication that leadership is not reserved for adults, as leadership opportunities come in various shapes and sizes for all ages.

Schools are an excellent place to develop student leadership skills. Students who practice making decisions and how to be adequately self-assured through modeling, role acting, appropriate supervision, and effective scaffolding of adults and more knowledgeable individuals. Students naturally become more independent in their social and academic life as they develop as leaders. By taking accountability, they show that they are willing to lend a hand to others, listen with empathy, and make wise decisions. Student leadership is crucial in developing students' leadership competencies in the classroom since it aids in the development of certain character traits (thecountryschool.org).

Acquiring leadership qualities among students enhances not only their personal growth but also their social relationships. It teaches them the value of looking out for one another both within and outside of the classroom, resolving conflicts in social situations on their own with the teacher's support and modeling, and choosing whether to play team sports and attend class. Almost everything involves leadership, including musicals, the outdoors education program, the playing field, the classroom, and students' leadership group. Opportunities abound, and peers, instructors, and advisors actively urge students to participate with the world around them.

In terms of sex, the majority of the officers were female which comprised 79 or 76.7% of the total number of respondents. The male officers comprised 24 or 23.3% of the pupil-officers.

Having the bigger number of SPG positions occupied by girls implies that student leadership is not absolutely for boys. The finding indicates that an equal opportunity to serve as student leaders in school is granted to both boys and girls which allow them to acquire and develop leadership skills necessary for their growth and development, especially as they integrate themselves in larger societies and perform their respective societal roles in the future.

Baroudi (2023) argues that encouraging female students to join clubs and organizations and immersing them in leadership activities both within and outside of the classroom can help them obtain real-world experience in managing and leading a group. Additionally, female students can collaborate closely with other organizations and take part in the real-world problem-solving that these organizations face through the partnership network that schools have. Giving female students these kinds of chances will help them become more innovative, creative, and proficient problem solvers. It will also expand their professional network.

In addition, providing females with opportunities to use their leadership abilities in a variety of settings, both inside and outside the classroom, would encourage them to take on leadership responsibilities and take part in the decision-making process. It is critical to close the gender equality gap in order to advance diversity and inclusion, social justice, expansion of the economy, and enhanced well-being. A developed human capital, wherein both genders have access to high-quality education and can produce a workforce that is more knowledgeable, competent, and capable, is a prerequisite for the general advancement and development of civilizations. This can be achieved through gender equality and female empowerment.

On the grade level of SPG officers, 46 or 44.7% are grade six pupils, 38 or 36.9% are grade five pupils, 15 or 14.6% belong to grade four, and 4 or 3.9% are grade three.

Student councils provide students, regardless of grade level, with the chance to develop their leadership skills and bring about constructive change in their schools and communities. Doherty (2023) emphasized that as efforts to teach the complete kid advance, there have been dynamic changes in schools over the past ten years. Deep learning, 21st century skills, and social-emotional learning integration have become standard demands.

The scaffolding of process competencies from a base of content knowledge is now common practice across curriculum standards. Educators seek out authentic learning opportunities, such as project-based learning, to help pupils to gain deeper knowledge and transferable skills. Student leadership development is woven throughout all these initiatives, but it's not always fully explored for our youngest learners. Elementary pupils need time and opportunities to build these skills in authentic ways.

Furthermore, as he "manifests itself on many levels," Todd Nesloney challenges educators in his book *When Kids Lead* to consider a more expansive definition of leadership. He argues that all children have the capacity to be leaders and adults have the duty to impart knowledge and create the environments necessary to help them realize this potential. Nesloney offers doable strategies for accomplishing both in order to empower children. The book's objectives are "to build awareness of the numerous possibilities that exist for students to exercise leadership within schools and to explain how to train students to capitalize on these opportunities" (Doherty, 2023).

A fourth-grader called Izzie wrote a letter to President Joe Biden recently expressing her desire to be the first female president. In the letter, Biden encouraged Izzie to follow her dreams and mentioned that a student council is a fantastic place to start. He posted the letter to his Instagram account.

For the positions in Supreme Pupil Government officers, 8 or 7.8% served as president, vice president, secretary, treasurer, auditor, and public information officers. Moreover, 39 or 37.9% were grade representatives, and 16 or 15.5% served as health protocol officers.

The above figures indicate that while there is a uniform number of officers for specific positions, the number of officers for grade

representatives and health protocols is bigger than the other positions. The increase in the number of grade representatives is dependent on the total number of enrolled pupils in a particular grade for a particular school year. However, in the case of health protocols, the position was introduced and the number was increased so that more pupil officers could assist in COVID 19 pandemic concerns in schools.

It takes more than just having a position to be a leader. Every day, someone leads without even realizing it. There is a belief that some people are naturally gifted leaders, and others have to learn how to lead. In any case, being a leader is a process exerting influence, working towards a shared objective, and—above all—building relationships based on trustworthiness and human connection. For each person, being a leader has a different meaning. It is a multifaceted idea, yet anyone may be a leader if they have the correct attitude and do not care who they are. According to Condit (2022), the ability to constantly present and conduct oneself in a favorable manner is a prerequisite for assuming the role of leadership.

In terms of socio-economic status, 61 or 59.2% of the Supreme Pupil Government officers belong to poor families, 37 or 35.9% are in the middle class, and 5 or 4.9% considered themselves as belonging to rich families.

The above figure infers that in spite of the poor economic status of the pupils, they can still serve as student leaders because the school is giving them the opportunity to acquire and develop skills in leadership as part of their preparation in performing their societal roles. This is in line with John Dewey's assertion that the best and deepest assurance of a larger society that is honorable, beautiful, and harmonious comes from schools that teach students how to become members of a community, instill in them a spirit of service, and provide them with the tools necessary for effective self-direction.

In spite of their financial hardship, educating and equipping students for leadership roles promotes a feeling of community and collaboration among peers. Dewey thought that by putting them in a community context, they would have a profound comprehension of the virtues of empathy, cooperation, and social responsibility, establishing in pupils a sincere desire to make a positive impact on the lives of others and society at large is essential to establishing in them the spirit of service. They are motivated to actively participate in deeds of kindness, assistance, and problem-solving for the benefit of their community and the wider world by cultivating a sense of service.

Giving kids the tools they need for self-direction and effective leadership development also entails giving them the information, abilities, and resources they need to manage their own lives and make wise choices. Fostering a culture of accountability and self-directed leadership among students can foster their sense of agency, autonomy, and critical thinking skills.

The aforementioned claims, however, contradict the research's findings, which show that first-generation and low-income students are less likely than their peers who come from higher-income households or who are not the first in their families to attend school to participate in leadership roles. Leadership roles present numerous opportunities for students, and it is especially worrisome that first-generation and low-income students might not be able to take advantage of the numerous advantages that frequently come with leadership roles (journalofleadershiped.org.).

Examining potential differences in first-generation and low-income students' school experiences—including their involvement as positional leaders of campus organizations—is crucial to understanding factors that may negatively influence their retention and scholastic attainment. Furthermore, for students from lower social classes and socio-economic backgrounds, the long-lasting effects of these disparities in educational attendance and attainment can yield many negative outcomes (researchgate.net).

Level of Leadership Competence of SPG Officers

The table below shows the leadership competence level of Supreme Pupil Government officers.

Table 3. *Leadership Competence Level of Supreme Pupil Government Officers*

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Planning	2.44	High
Implementation	2.40	High
Monitoring and Evaluation	2.42	High
Student Representation	2.38	High
Overall Total	2.41	High

Table 3 indicates that on the level of leadership competence of Supreme Pupil Government officers, planning obtained the highest mean score of 2.44, followed by monitoring and evaluation, with a mean of 2.42; implementation obtained a mean of 2.40, and student representation with 2.38. Overall, the total mean score is 2.41 which means that the level of leadership competence of the pupil leaders is high.

The finding implies that the school has a strong and efficient system of student governance. This high degree of competency indicates that SPG officers possess the fundamental leadership abilities needed to create and carry out detailed plans, supervise and guarantee the accomplishment of projects, keep tabs on developments, assess results, and effectively represent the student body. This encourages

active student participation in school activities and decision-making processes, creates a healthy school climate, and results in a more empowered and involved student body.

Numerous reasons can be responsible for kids' high levels of leadership competence. Studies indicate that a student's capacity to lead can be enhanced by a number of professional competencies, such as the capacity for inspiring others, evidence-based approach, clear vision, strategic planning, effective communication, and appreciation for experts. Additionally, by cultivating leadership traits via practice, feedback, and self-evaluation, students' degree of leadership competency can be raised. Motivating pupils to be really interested in other people, actively listen, and provide encouragement and participation in introspective activities can also help them develop their leadership abilities.

In accordance with DepEd's policies and procedures (2019), SPG officers can develop the abilities and know-how to carefully design and carry out initiatives, track their development, assess results, and fairly represent the interests of the student body. This competency level promotes democratic values and student leadership development, which improves the overall educational experience, creates a healthy school climate, and motivates active student participation. The entire student body will gain from the increased likelihood of success for the school's objectives (DepEd Order 47, s. 2014).

It is critical to understand that developing students' leadership competency requires a blend of character attributes, learnt abilities, and ongoing development as a result of exposure to leadership models, initiatives, and growth opportunities. Successful leadership has a major impact on future professional readiness, personal growth, and academic achievement.

Level of Leadership Competence of SPG Officers in terms of Profile

The following table shows the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupil Government officers when grouped according to pupils' profiles.

Table 4. *Leadership Competence Level of SPG Officers in Terms of Profile*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Age	2.48	High
Sex	2.40	High
Grade Level	2.38	High
Position	2.45	High
Socioeconomic Status	2.52	High
Overall Mean	2.44	High

Table 4 reveals that in the level of leadership competence of Supreme Pupil Government officers, when grouped according to their profile, socioeconomic status obtained the highest mean of 2.52, followed by age (2.48), position (2.45), sex (2.40), and grade level gaining the lowest mean of 2.38. Overall, the overall mean of 2.44 delivered a high level of leadership competence.

The results imply that the student government has a diverse and inclusive leadership structure. This high level of competence suggests that SPG officers, irrespective of their demographic backgrounds, have the skills and knowledge required to efficiently plan, carry out, monitor, and evaluate projects as well as represent the student body (DepEd, 2019). In the end, this inclusivity improves the overall efficacy and influence of the student government by creating a varied and egalitarian atmosphere that encourages active engagement and collaboration among students from all backgrounds.

Furthermore, Lugtu (2020) stressed that organizational structure or the position of pupils in the SPG has nothing to do with their academics. They must balance their time and energy for both aspects if they want to excel in both areas. However, they cannot expect that if they are doing well as servants, they will also do well in their studies. More so, Siscar and Ojales (2021) stated that for an organization to work effectively and efficiently, it must listen to the critics of its constituents, which are the learners. They are the ones they are serving. Therefore, their voices must be heard.

Age and Leadership Competence

Gaining a rating of high in their leadership competence in terms of age implies that student leaders in the elementary level can serve as effective leaders and be of service to the school when properly guided and trained for leadership responsibilities, indicating that age is not a liability in leadership.

The aforementioned results corroborate Vision's (2018) findings, which indicate that the study's results were inconsistent and that there has been a recent, more encouraging trend regarding younger people's inclination to assume leadership roles. Furthermore, the findings in the study of Bell (2018) demonstrated that transformational leadership, regardless of age, was just as successful in encouraging subordinates to have positive work attitudes.

Bolander et al. (2019) stated that it could take some time for a young individual to consider themselves as a manager or leader before they have all this experience. Researches that tracked eight inexperienced managers over time came to the conclusion that the managers' professional identities were continually vacillating due to a dialectic between continuity and change, advancement and stagnation, knowledge and ignorance, and hope and hopelessness. According to the findings, the greatest approach to assist aspiring leaders in

assuming leadership roles is to concentrate on gaining knowledge from the difficulties, issues, and conundrums that managers encounter on a daily basis (Bolander, et al., 2019).

As a result, it is praiseworthy that primary schools train and prepare the leaders of tomorrow's society. It is imperative that student leaders get ready for the future since present leaders will inevitably age and require replacement, ensuring societal improvement (Balayon, 2019).

Therefore, because age affects experience, maturity, and perspective, it plays a big role in leadership growth. While younger student officers might be full of energy and new ideas, it is possible that they lack the maturity and real-world experience necessary to make difficult decisions. They become more emotionally intelligent, more self-aware, and possess the strategic thinking abilities that are essential for good leadership as they mature and gain experience.

Sex and Leadership Competence

Getting a high ranking in their leadership competence in terms of sex suggests that regardless of whether the student leaders are male or female, they can be effective leaders

and of great value to the school. This reflection may provide an answer to the call of the United Nations (2018) for all sectors of society to mobilize based on three levels: actions at global levels to ensure greater leadership, actions at local levels, especially in schools, and actions by individuals, in this sense including youth and, with it, student leadership.

Nonetheless, men continue to hold a disproportionate number of key leadership jobs, and there is a significant and critical gender gap in these roles. Despite decades of intensive research on leadership in general and a wealth of school-based initiatives centered on providing undergraduate students with leadership experiences, these gaps still exist. One

of the many social and economic reasons influencing gender disparities in leadership roles may be the lack of adequate support from our higher education system for female students' leadership goals during their college years. The paucity of empirical research examining leadership emergence in adolescence (Tackett et al., 2022) and in college-aged populations (Correia-Harker & Dugan, 2020) further complicates our ability to address gender inequities.

It is interesting to note that when determining which of the two sexes would have the highest number of pupils aspiring to leadership roles, gender or sex may not even be taken into consideration. Yet, little is known about how gender identity influences leadership aspirations in undergraduate college students or the extent to which educational experiences and institutional environments may influence a different development of leadership aspirations across genders, despite the fact that emerging adults are clearly interested in developing their leadership skills and motivations (Tackett et al., 2022).

Because of this, scholars have called for further long-term studies on how leadership develops during college, paying particular emphasis to how collegiate experiences affect this development (Correia-Harker & Dugan, 2020). Though they also predict later wealth, educational attainment, life satisfaction, and even longevity, leadership goals and motives are important determinants of later leadership results (Offermann et al., 2020).

Scheuer and Loughlin (2020) report that an experimental vignette research that looked at older workers' perceptions of younger bosses studied the interaction of age and gender. The study emphasizes how older men have historically been stereotyped as leaders since these preconceptions are biased against older men in addition to being male. The findings of Scheuer and Loughlin demonstrate that senior employees favor communal traits in a leader, but they also believe when supervisors are portrayed as older than their direct reports, this is most favorable. The findings also showed that young male leaders are generally viewed less favorably than young female leaders in the same role if their supervisors lack communal traits. It is uncertain if subordinates' assessments of their actual leaders, regardless of gender, are influenced by these judgments of leadership competence.

Grade Level and Leadership Competence of SPG Officers

Obtaining a high rating in their leadership competence in terms of their grade level presupposes that the SPG officers have received motivation and training from their advisers in the soft skills.

As stated by Asbari et al. (2020), 86% of the core competencies for student leaders are soft competencies. Hard competencies, such as using a computer, are categorized into three categories, along with soft competencies, time management, and mixed competencies, such as interviewing a subordinate. The aforementioned observation aligns with these categories. These consist of adaptability, interpersonal and problem-solving abilities, teamwork, communication skills, and work ethic. This demonstrates that creating unique programs to enhance the leadership skills of aspiring professionals is feasible (Barnes, 2020).

The range of duties and demands put on student officers are directly correlated with grade level. With an emphasis on assignments and group dynamics, lower-grade pupils may have more constrained leadership positions. As kids go through the grades, their leadership duties could broaden to encompass mentoring younger students, strategic planning, and problem-solving. Over time, this evolution enables individuals to acquire more sophisticated leadership abilities.

Any subject can benefit from leadership, and it can be successfully introduced as early as elementary school. As one of the key goals

of student development that instructional strategies attempt to accomplish, leadership holds a significant position within various learning types (Hishamuddin & Shukor, 2021; Herrera & Lucas, 2020). In the long run, leadership can be a major career-building influence as well as a strong predictor of graduates' ability to find employment.

The capacity to demonstrate leadership in a variety of social and professional contexts is a crucial professional talent for future specialists, much as the primary students in the forefront now (Faraj Allah et al., 2018). Empirical research frequently shows that people who exhibit or acquire leadership traits have more motivation and lower anxiety when learning (Rau, Citation 2018). One way that a student might demonstrate leadership is through an activity that they already engage in but still need to work on (Mizintseva et al., 2018; Yu, 2019). According to Tanaka-Ellis & Sekiguchi (2019; Tatman, 2021) leadership is typically viewed as a trait that is acquired via participation in group projects, interactions with teachers, and online communication.

Position and Leadership Competence of SPG Officers

Getting a high mark in leadership competence in terms of their position in the student organization infers that whatever position student leaders hold the measurement of success will always be their performance in promoting student success as entrusted with significant responsibilities. A student's standing inside a club or organization is a major factor in determining their access to leadership opportunities. Students who hold leadership roles can practice accountability, delegation, and decision-making. Their confidence, communication skills, and problem-solving ability all improve as a result of these encounters. It is crucial to remember that students can exhibit leadership abilities even in the absence of official roles, as there are many other methods for leadership to appear (Dedicatoria, et al. 2023).

Aymoldanovna, et al. (2019) claim that creating a student government gives leaders a chance to participate actively in the educational process. Student leaders who join organizations take on duties beyond their jobs and titles (Dong et al., 2023). According to Bekar et al.'s study from 2023, student leaders would acquire strong communication skills that would emphasize their interpersonal abilities in leading their peers as they freely connect with others and carry out the responsibilities that come with each of their individual positions in the organizations. Additionally, Kern and Selamat (2022) backed up these assertions, stating that good student leaders should understand how to create a welcoming environment, promote peer collaboration, and assist in the many endeavors of their fellow students. They should also act as an example that reflects the hopes and dreams of all students, demonstrating empathy, fortitude, and flexibility in order to create a supportive learning atmosphere.

Hu (2023) highlights that one of the strongest motivators is the aspiration to make a significant contribution to the academic community and engage in collaborative activities. According to Chen and Zhang (2023), students who join student organizations seek to enhance their leadership abilities, feel a sense of community, and grow personally. When students take on leadership positions in their organizations, they take on duties that necessitate developing important skills like teamwork, time management, and decision-making (Sebaly, 2023).

Socio-Economic Status and Leadership Competence

For Supreme Government Officers to obtain a high score in leadership competence in terms of their socio-economic status suggests that being economically-disadvantaged does not stand in the way for the student leaders to perform and function properly in order to contribute more fully to the overall achievement of the school.

The foregoing claim exalts the study of Guohua, et al on "Does Family Background Affect the Experience of College Student Leaders?" who assert that the result of their empirical study showed that family background has an effect on the fairness of educational process. Pupils with privileged family backgrounds are more likely to become student leaders. The two that have the most effects are the father's job unit and degree of education. This is due to the fact that having a strong family background increases social, cultural, and economic capital—of which the family's economic capital will give the kids access to a variety of educational resources throughout their schooling (Guohua, et al., 2024).

However, the authors highlight that having city household registration has no obvious effect on students serving as class leaders, but the probability of poor students serving as various kinds of student leaders is higher than that of non-poor students. This is different from the conclusion of most literature. According to previous studies, family economic capital is the source of resources invested in children's education. Students from families with better economic conditions have better knowledge and personality than students with weaker economic condition, and are more likely to be favored by classmates and teachers.

Nonetheless, this paper's empirical findings demonstrate that there is a higher likelihood of impoverished students becoming student leaders than there is of wealthy students. There are a few potential explanations: Compared to non-poor students, poor students engage in fewer extracurricular activities, are more willing to dedicate a significant amount of time to studying, and are more capable of autonomous learning. Additionally, they understand that diligence and social practice.

The study's empirical findings demonstrate that there is a higher likelihood of impoverished students becoming student leaders than there is of wealthy students. There are a few potential explanations: Compared to non-poor students, poor students engage in fewer extracurricular activities, are more willing to dedicate a significant amount of time to studying, and are more capable of autonomous learning. Additionally, students are more conscious that the most effective approaches to close this gap are through academic effort

and social practice (Guohua, et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the Great Famine in China, which occurred between the ages of 6 and 13 and was a time of significant socio-economic adversity, had a negative and exponential impact on children who later became corporate CEOs' strategic risk-taking behavior, according to a study by Tian et al. (2022).

The relationship between early SES and self-control has a lot of evidence behind it. For instance, according to parent ratings in each case (Holmes et al., 2019), the SES of children 3.5 years old predicted effortful control six months later (Lecheile et al., 2020), and the SES of children 8.5 years old predicted self-control concurrently and through age 15. In a different study, men's leadership role occupancy was positively correlated with family SES, but women's was adversely correlated (Liu et al., 2021). Conversely, people with high SES typically feel freer and value their own agency more, which makes them more willing to take chances and be more proactive in relationships (Fang and Saks, 2021).

Socio-economic status (SES) has an impact on who has access to opportunities, networks, and resources that help build leadership skills. Higher SES students might have more access to mentoring, leadership opportunities, and educational resources. Socio-economic hurdles, however, are not insurmountable. Even students from lower socio-economic backgrounds can become good leaders if they actively look for opportunities, volunteer in the community, and focus on their abilities.

Academic Performance of SPG Officers

The following table shows the academic performance of the officers of the Supreme Pupil Government.

Table 5. Academic Performance of Supreme Pupil Government Officers

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Overall Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Outstanding	94	92.07	
Very Satisfactory	9		
Satisfactory	0		Outstanding
Fair Satisfactory	0		
Did Not Meet Expectations	0		
Total	103		

Table 5 shows that 94 out of 103 officers of the Supreme Pupil Government earned an outstanding academic performance, 9 have a very satisfactory academic performance. With overall mean of 92.07, the academic performance of SPG officers as a whole, is outstanding.

The above value shows that most pupil leaders are performing well academically despite the seemingly arduous responsibilities they need to perform for the benefit of students and the school. It conforms to the findings of Irsheid (2018), who claimed that his research has established that involving students in leadership roles in schools is one of the determinants of the academic performance of the latter. First, student leaders are able to make correct decisions which impact the decisions they make in their academic lives. Leadership also allows the students to take part in decision-making in schools which, in turn influence managerial decisions as well as policy formulation in the schools. In this case, the schools are able to formulate policies that boost the academic achievement of the students. Further, the ability to collaborate that is developed as a result of leadership roles also enhances the performance of the students. Therefore, in this context, leadership has been noted to directly contribute to the improved academic performance of the student learners.

On the other hand, a study reveals that a significant number of student leaders encounter challenges while executing their responsibilities. Engaging in student leadership activities may impede academic performance. Primarily, the issue is attributed to time since student leaders are likely giving more time to their duties as leaders as compared to their academic obligations (Mjrage, et al, 2019). Moreover, excessive workload takes away valuable time that could be spent on academic work (Tucay, et al, 2021).

Managing pressure is the first coping strategy that the student leaders disclosed for overcoming obstacles. First and foremost, the weight of their tasks is increased significantly by the demand to be excellent role models and capable leaders in addition to their considerable responsibilities (Rizzo, et al, 2021).

Burnout is another factor that could have an impact on student leaders' academic achievement. Numerous studies have demonstrated the detrimental effects of burnout on people's lives in general and productivity in particular. According to the participants, they become burned out when planning a series of events back-to-back. Student leaders may experience pressure from planning consecutive events, which could lead to them putting off or cramming their academic obligations. Eventually, this causes students to experience burnout (Atienza, et al, 2022).

Mueller (2020) contends that sensible priority-setting, on the other hand, can help to reduce personal worries by facilitating effective planning and the achievement of both professional and personal objectives, which will provide favorable results. As a result, tasks need to be prioritized in order to prevent workload accumulation. By doing this, pupils are able to reduce their stress levels from an excessive workload (Mueller, S. 2020). Additionally, the concerned student possesses free will and choice. It is evident that students have options,

and it is up to them to decide whether to put their studies ahead of their leadership duties or the other way around (Abenoja, et al, 2019).

Difference in the Level of Leadership Competence of SPG Officers According to Pupils' Profile

The following table shows the difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupil Government officers when grouped according to the pupils' profile.

Table 6. *Difference in the Leadership Competence Level of the SPG Officers According to Age*

Age	f	Mean Rank
8-9 years old	1	80.00
10-11 years old	30	51.15
12-13 years old	54	51.18
14-15 years old	18	54.33
Total	103	

Kruskal-Wallis H: 1.058

p-value: 0.787

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table reveals the computed value is 1.058, and the p-value of 0.787 means that there is no significant difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupils Government officers according to age. Myatt (2022) emphasized that skill, not age, is what matters in leadership. There are countless examples of successful and unsuccessful leaders throughout history. The intangibles—passion, character, dedication, talent, and discernment—are far more significant than a person's birthdate. Whether you are a Boomer, Gen X, or Gen Y, I do not care; what matters to me is your ability to contribute. I shall present you with an alternative viewpoint on ageism in today's post (Myatt, 2022).

Alagu (2023) in her article *Does Age Matter in Leadership?* has noted that it is similar to wondering if height matters in athletics or whether age matters in leadership. Undoubtedly, she said, a portion of the response relies on the sport and stance one adopts. Effective leadership is influenced by age, but not in the way one might assume. She emphasizes that aging brings three attributes that might enhance one's capacity for leadership skills. First, growing older offers one a new perspective on past events. If one has never walked in another person's shoes, it can be difficult to imagine oneself there. Wisdom and failure-based knowledge come with age. Second, growing older offers the chance to fail several times before succeeding, which can provide insightful knowledge about what works and what doesn't. As a leader, this understanding will help the individual establish trust with others by demonstrating resilience, commitment, and perseverance. Third, maturity makes one more resilient to criticism. When someone is younger, they are more susceptible to internalizing criticism and developing self-doubt. People get a thick skin over time as a result of learning from their experiences and determining what is best for them. Because of this, it is simpler for individuals to take constructive criticism from others without getting irritated or offended. The quick response is that leadership is unaffected by age. Being a leader is something that one may do at any age. Age and wisdom are not synonymous (Alagu, 2023).

Table 7. *Difference in the Leadership Competence Level of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers According to Sex*

Sex	f	Mean Rank
Male	24	51.94
Female	79	52.02
Total	103	

Mann-Whitney U: 946.50

p-value: 0.991

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of significance

Using the Mann-Whitney U Test, the table reveals the computed value is 946.50, and the p-value of 0.991 means that there is no significant difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupils Government officers according to sex. In the article published by Federer Performance Management Group in 2018 entitled *Does Gender Matter in Business Leadership? Yes and No*, emphasis was given that in leadership, there are differences between the sexes – biological, psychological, nurture, nature, etc. The main differences that come into play in leadership roles for women are style and emotional tendencies. There are no differences – and this is supported by research but really should be self-evident – between men and women when it comes to ability in leadership positions. But style and emotional profile do matter and can be both positive and negative (FPMG, 2018).

Men tend to be more authoritarian and directive in their leadership styles, whereas women typically exhibit more democratic and participatory traits. Women are also more likely to offer rewards and exhibit transformational leadership, which is essentially acting as role models. Both the transactional leadership trait of punishment and a laissez-faire attitude (neglect of responsibilities) were more prevalent in men. It should be noted that these are only trends. Both men and women abound whose leadership philosophies align more with the preferences of the other sex. Each person is unique.

Furthermore, style plays a big part in successful leadership; yet, various styles are more effective in certain contexts. Democratic and transformative leadership qualities are typically exhibited by highly successful women. But in the business world, things can be a little

different. In certain professional environments, women may need to adopt a more stereotypically "male" leadership style that emphasizes hierarchical decision-making and single decision-making in order to advance. Though they have a stronger "voice" and style, a number of women leaders defy the stereotypes associated with women. As they try to climb the figurative ladder, they regrettably encounter increasing resistance and unfavorable comments more frequently. In my experience, however, certain fundamental abilities are gender-neutral in leadership. Gender is important, yet depending on the situation, it may be advantageous or disadvantageous. More "male" inclinations are required in certain circumstances, and more "female" traits in others. The majority of research on the distinctions between male and female managers' leadership philosophies revealed that they operate differently. Men tend to be more task-oriented and dominating, whereas women are more likely to have relationship styles.

Table 8. *Difference in the Leadership Competence Level of the Supreme Pupil Government Officers According to Grade Level*

Grade Level	<i>f</i>	Mean Rank
Grade III	4	41.88
Grade IV	15	50.63
Grade V	38	51.03
Grade VI	46	54.13
Total	103	

Kruskal-Wallis H: 0.769

p-value: 0.857

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table reveals the computed value is 0.769. The p-value of 0.857 means that there is no significant difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupils Government officers according to grade level. In the article published by Teach Starter and authored by Natalie (2022) entitled Leadership Activities for Kids to Build Leader Skills in the Classroom, the account emphasized that as students grow older, there is a certain amount of responsibility placed on their shoulders. Regardless of whether they are the most senior class on campus or have "official" leadership posts, students must recognize the significance of their responsibilities as student leaders and the attributes they must have. More than merely guiding a new student through the classroom's procedures is involved in being a student leader. The goal is to develop into an autonomous thinker who can collaborate well with others and have a positive impact on those around them (teachstarter.com, 2022).

Even young children can acquire and develop leadership abilities when they are specifically taught and given opportunities to lead, according to study, even though some people are born leaders. Assuming constructivism, as our teacher team does, means that children can gradually acquire leadership abilities by incorporating prior information into fresh perspectives on the world (teachstarter.com., 2022).

Teaching pupils to be leaders requires encouraging self-reflection, teamwork, and critical thinking. According to Daniels, et al. (202) research, group reflective learning is a successful technique in which students assess their behaviors and mental processes through talks. This results in better professional practices.

The aforementioned claims are backed up by Vygotsky's scaffolding, often known as scaffolding, a method that teachers and capable students employ in the classroom to assist students who are in their Zone Proximal Development. When teaching elementary students how to be student leaders, the teacher and student collaborate at first. The instructor demonstrates the majority of the work and explains the reasoning behind it, so the student is better able to understand the material. When a student gains more familiarity with the subject matter, the teacher's support decreases and more of the works are completed by the student independently. The scaffolding gets progressively less until the pupil has grasped the material and is able to operate without it (Vygotsky).

The table below presents the difference in leadership competence level of the Supreme Government Officers according to position.

Table 9. *Difference in the Leadership Competence Level of Supreme Pupil Government Officers According to Position*

Position	<i>f</i>	Mean Rank
President	8	71.75
Vice President	8	44.13
Secretary	8	36.38
Treasurer	8	46.94
Auditor	8	70.69
PIO	8	60.94
Health Protocol	16	66.88
Grade Representatives	39	42.04
Total	103	

Kruskal-Wallis H: 18.705

p-value: 0.009

Decision: Reject H_0

Interpretation: Significant at 5% level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table reveals the computed value is 18.705. The p-value of 0.009 means that there is a significant difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupil government officers according to position.

Although having a position in the student organization allows one to serve, when a position is improperly illustrated, it is not the only thing that matters. Dadi (2020) states that "Leadership is action, not a position," citing Donald Mc Gannon. This implies that a person's choice of action rather than the position they have within an organization determines their level of leadership. It all comes down to behavior and decision. No matter where you are in the company, adopting a leadership style will get you respect; being a leader does not require a title or a position.

People are more likely to follow a leader who sets an example for them. Motivating those around him to push themselves is a component of his role as a leader. He has to lead the way by example in order to do this. What he values most in others, particularly those who report to him, will be firmly established by his working style and attitude towards others. Others are encouraged to do the same by upholding professional standards and working to a high quality (Dadi 2020).

Dadi (2020) emphasized further those mistakes are inevitable for everyone. Acknowledging and taking responsibility for one's errors indicates honesty and receptivity to helpful criticism, two qualities shared by those with a high level of integrity in the workplace. After the team fails, the leader can accept accountability and blame and then individually coach and mentor the group.

Furthermore, it is likely that there will be occasions when an individual really disagrees with the viewpoint of another person, regardless of how wonderful the workplace may be. Even though they disagree with the other person's viewpoint, it is still crucial in these situations to show respect, listen, and consider what they have to say (Dadi 2020).

Great leaders do not require frequent pats on the back; instead, they actively look for chances to assist others and ask for assistance when necessary. Even if it may sound archaic, one can be both modest and assertive at the same time. They are compatible, yes. genuinely modest people embrace their own advantages and disadvantages without becoming defensive or passing judgment. They can be forceful by peacefully and positively defending their own or other people's rights, as opposed to being hostile or acquiescing in wrongdoing. Never should a leader claim credit for the work that their subordinates accomplish. As an alternative, he should show compassion, cherish each individual, and acknowledge them all (Dadi 2020).

Table 10. *Difference in the Leadership Competence Level of Supreme Pupil Government Officers According to Socio-Economic Status*

<i>Socioeconomic Status</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Poor	61	46.56
Middle	37	57.14
Rich	5	80.40
Total	103	

Kruskal-Wallis H: 7.671
p-value: 0.022
Decision: Reject Ho
Interpretation: Significant at 5% level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table reveals the computed value is 7.671 and the p-value of 0.022 means that there is a significant difference in the level of leadership competence of the Supreme Pupil government officers according to socio-economic status.

Serving as student leaders can be very challenging for elementary pupils and leadership can result to several limitations. One of them can be the low economic status of the families of some of the students which may render them incapable of spending for their personal and school needs which may stand in the way for them to perform better as student leaders. More often, deprivation is the consequence of a lack of income and other resources.

Tan (2018) pointed out in his study that different leadership practices have different effects depending on one's socio-economic position. Generally speaking, he made the observation that leadership approaches such as instructional leadership might make up for lack of educational resources in low socio-economic contexts by emphasizing achievement more than before (Tan, 2018). As it happens, a number of instructional characteristics have the potential to raise achievement, particularly for kids from lower socio-economic backgrounds.

According to recent empirical research, leadership behaviors can help low-SES kids perform more because they make up for resource disparities in the school (Steinberg & Yang, 2020; Tan et al., 2020).

Therefore, in order to make up for a disparity between schools, the school administrator must make up for a shortage of resources, but making up for a difference inside the school entails making up for a shortage of resources for students.

Relationship Between the Level of Leadership Competence and Academic Performance of SPG Officers

The following table shows the relationship between the level of leadership competence and the academic performance of Supreme Pupil Government officers.

Table 11. *Relationship Between the Leadership Competence Level and Academic Performance of Supreme Pupil Government Officers*

Leadership Competence Level	Academic Performance					Total
	Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fair	Did Not Meet	
High	51	6	0	0	0	57
Moderate	42	3	0	0	0	45
Low	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total	94	9	0	0	0	103

Computed Gamma value: -0.261

P-value: 0.447

Decision: Accept H_0

Interpretation: Not Significant at 5% level of Significance

Using the Gamma Coefficient, the table indicates the computed value is -0.261. The p-value of 0.447 means that there is no significant relationship between the level of leadership competence and academic performance of the Supreme Pupil Government officers. Aymoldanovna, et al. (2019) claim that creating a student government gives leaders the chance to participate actively in the educational process. Although student leadership has shown to improve academic performance, several researches have raised concerns. Despite having more duties, student leaders frequently perform better in class than their peers, according to a Fuentes et al. (2020) study. However, Afalla (2020) notes that a student's participation in extracurricular activities, such as student leadership, may not be directly correlated with their academic success, emphasizing the uniqueness of student leaders.

Student participation in extracurricular activities is strongly correlated with increased attendance, behavior, and academic success, according to Reeves (2018). Students who engage in extracurricular activities, generally, outperform their non-participating peers, according to Reeves (2018). Playing sports and taking part in other school-sponsored events are examples of this involvement. Learners who are regularly exposed to music outperform those who are not. While learning and development environments for students may be enhanced by involvement opportunities, it is important for educators to provide “the scaffolding, structure, and environment to facilitate and shape students’ learning and development” (Haber-Curran, 2019).

Conclusions

Supreme pupil government officers comprise mostly of 12-13 years old, female, grade six pupils, with complete set of officers namely: president, vice president, secretary, treasurer, auditor, and public information officer, health protocols, and grade representatives. The respondents consider their socio-economic status as poor.

The level of leadership competence of Supreme Pupil Government officers in terms planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and student representation, is high.

The level of leadership competence of SPG officers in terms of their profile is high.

The academic performance of SPG officers is outstanding.

There is no significant difference in the level of leadership competence of SPG officers according to age, sex, grade level. However, there is a significant difference in position and socio-economic status.

There is no significant relationship between the level of leadership competence and academic performance of the SPG officers.

The school division superintendent can articulate a clear vision and goals in implementing student government in all schools in the whole division. The vision should outline the desired outcomes and benefits of student government which include providing a platform for students to express their ideas, concerns, and needs. The program would also foster students’ leadership abilities which include decision-making, communication, and collaboration.

The public school district supervisors may develop a comprehensive framework for student government that should address key aspects of the program such as defining the roles and responsibilities of different schools in the district, establishing clear and fair election procedures, including eligibility criteria campaign guidelines, and voting mechanisms, and ensure an effective fund management, budgeting, accountability, and transparency.

School administrators may be involved in supporting student government initiatives and providing guidance to student leaders. They can provide the students with the resources and training they need to take ownership of their roles, encourage them to participate in decision-making processes, and provide feedback on program initiatives, and support student-led projects and initiatives that address issues relevant to students.

Teachers and SPG advisers may create an environment where student leaders feel comfortable sharing their ideas, concerns, and suggestions, actively listen to their perspectives, and incorporate them into organizational discussions and decision-making processes. They can offer workshops or training sessions on leadership skills, including communication, teamwork, conflict resolution, and decision-making. They can also educate student leaders on the school’s policies, procedures, and guidelines related to student government. This includes understanding the student government constitution, meeting protocols, and financial management.

Parents can encourage their children to consider running for a position in student government. They can explain the benefits of participation, such as developing leadership skills, gaining experience in decision-making, and contributing to the school community. They can also show their support by attending student government meetings, school events, and activities organized by student officers. This demonstrates their interest and encouragement of their children's involvement.

Students would be encouraged to participate in student government because it provides them a platform for them to express their ideas, concerns, and needs, directly impacting school policies, events and initiatives. They can also be allowed to attend student government meetings to understand the issues being discussed, the decision-making process, and the opportunities for student involvement. They can share ideas, perspectives, and concerns during the meetings and discussions. By understanding the benefits, exploring different roles, getting involved, and continuously seeking growth, they will gain valuable skills and experiences that will serve them well throughout their academic and professional journeys.

Future researchers can delve deeper into the complexities of student government's impact on diverse student populations, including marginalized groups, students with disabilities, and those from low-income backgrounds. They also investigate how student government structures and practices can promote equity, address systemic inequalities, and create a more inclusive school environment for all students. Moreover, their research should consider how student government operates within the context of larger societal issues, such as political polarization, social justice movements, and educational policy reforms.

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